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Marine eukaryote and HAB monitoring in Japan with next generation technology

Sequencing technologies such as Illumina MiSeq have made it possible to obtain billions of sequence reads in a single experiment. Massively parallel sequencing (MPS) is revolutionizing surveys of eukaryotic diversity, including harmful algal bloom (HAB) species. This technology enables us to detect several hundreds of operational taxonomic units (OTUs) of eukaryotes from seawater samples and facilitates the detection of low-abundance populations in complex eukaryote communities. The eastern part of Hokkaido facing the Okhotsk Sea is where the coldest water (-2°C) flows in from Sakhalin in the winter. The marine ecosystem in this area has been considered sensitive to perturbations in environmental conditions. Mombetsu city is thus recognized as the most important monitoring base for observing plankton biodiversity in

the coldest waters of Japan. Plankton biodiversity has been performed using MPS-based technology once a week, from April 2012 until present day at Mombetsu city. The Mombetsu city office also has carried out daily environmental monitoring such as water temperature and salinity since 1996, and morphology-based monitoring of zooplankton sampled using nets more than once a week since 1997. In this study, a monitoring survey of eukaryote biodiversity using the MPS-based technique was performed. Surprisingly, many HAB species were detected in northern Hokkaido.

Water temperature, salinity, and chlorophyll-fluorescence were measured weekly with a CTD from April 10 2012 to June 2, 2014 ($n = 112$) at the Okhotsk tower in Okhotsk Sea (Mombetsu city, Japan) ($44^{\circ}20.22'N$, $143^{\circ}22.85'E$) and

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A follow-up special session on dinoflagellate cysts is scheduled during the ICHA 2018 in Nantes, and will ensure the transfer of expertise and uptake of methods internationally (see p. 17).

Anyone interested in this session can contact: Kenneth.mertens@ifremer.fr or Kirsty.Smith@cawthron.org.nz

Fig. 1. A plot of non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) analysis for the eukaryotic biodiversity survey using the MPS-based technique in the seawater samples of Okhotsk Sea. The similarity index was calculated using the Jaccard index.

the surface data was used in this study. Surface seawater (0.5 L) was collected weekly with a plastic bucket during the same period. For MPS-based monitoring based on amplicon-seq of 18S-rRNA gene (V7–9 region), PCR amplification and 454 pyrosequencing were performed according to Nagai *et al* [1, 2].

Water temperature, salinity, and chlorophyll *a* measurement ranges were -1.6-22.4°C, 18.3-33.7 PSU, and <0.0-9.8 µg L⁻¹ during the survey period. Even during mid-summer, the surface water temperature did not reach 23°C, and it decreased to below -1.5°C in mid-winter. Relatively high chlorophyll *a* concentrations produced by microalgal blooms were observed in samples taken during the warm water seasons during the survey. This is not a common phenomenon as dense microalgal blooms, i.e. red tide formation, have often been confirmed below sea ice in mid-winter.

The number of OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units = species richness) ranged from 101 to 454 (266 ± 70 = average ± SD). To minimize the influence of this bias on further analyses, random re-sampling of the MPS was performed on samples with the minimum number of MPS (2,908), and the OTUs were rarefied. The re-calculated OTUs were 89-267 (179 ± 44). These numbers were similar to those at the Seto Inland Sea

and Yatsushiro Sea in Japan, which are considered to be eutrophic waters (Nagai *et al* unpublished data), suggesting nutrient rich environments in the Okhotsk Sea [3]. The observed richness (= OTUs) per eukaryotic environmental sample estimated using the MPS-based method was 383-2,133 [4], 1,229-1,823 [5], and 942-1,756 [6]. Estimations of the number of OTUs vary depending on the platform used for MPS data treatment, and are also affected by universal primers. Therefore, the plankton richness or diversity in different ecosystems estimated using different platforms could not be compared directly.

The variability of plankton biodiversity among samples was evaluated by applying similarity indices (the Jaccard index), and non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) analysis was performed (Fig. 1). Samples taken in the same month but from different years were more closely plotted and also the samples of closest months were located in the closest positions, showing the consecutive transition of species composition and the clear seasonal pattern in Okhotsk Sea. Interestingly, the samples were plotted more closely in winter than those at summer seasons, indicating that limited species can appear in severe winter conditions.

For comparison among the super group levels, frequencies of the OTUs

and the MPSs, which were identical to those in International Nucleotide Sequence Databases (INSDs) showing > 0.990 blast top hit similarity, were calculated in each super group (Fig. 2). In the Apusozoa, Amoebozoa, and unclassified groups, the detected OTUs were less than 10 (data not shown). Their frequencies within the OTUs and the MPSs were 20.6-79.4% and 55.7-96.0%, and these data varied depending on the super groups (Fig. 2). The frequencies of OTUs and the MPSs, which were identified as a single species, were 11.9-41.2% and 30.9-70.4%, respectively. The taxonomic identification power was relatively high in Archaeplastida, Opisthokonta, and Viridiplantae, but low in Alveolata and Rhizaria, especially in Rhizaria (less than the half of Alveolata). The Rhizaria data probably results from the difficulty of the classification by morphology-based observation due to the delicacy of the cells (good fixation methods are not available) and the difficulty to maintain them as culture strains (heterotrophs require appropriate prey sources). The frequencies of OTUs and the MPSs, which were identical to those at more than two species including sp., were 5.5-38.2% and 0.6-58.6%, respectively. The frequencies of OTUs and the MPSs, which were identical to a single top hit but identified as sp., were 0.0-10.6% and 0.0-33.5%, respectively. Three important factors that influence the power of taxonomic identification are 1) the variability of the target gene sequences among species, 2) the quality and the length of next generation sequences, 3) the depth of INSDs [7, 8].

Surprisingly, the genera *Alexandrium*, *Azadinium*, *Chattonella*, *Cochlodinium*, *Karenia*, *Karlodinium*, *Proocentrum*, *Pseudochattonella*, and *Takayama* were detected, including toxic and fish-killing species in Okhotsk Sea. *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* was detected mainly during summer survey periods. To ascertain the origin of the Sea of Japan population of *C. polykrikoides* (East Asian clade [9]), 13 samples, isolated from 11 different localities in Japanese and Korean coastal waters, were analyzed using 10 polymorphic microsatellites [10]. Population genetic analyses identified three clusters – the Sea of Japan populations, Yatsushiro Sea (Kumamoto Pref.) populations, and other populations – indicating genetic

Fig. 2. Frequencies of the number of OTUs showing >0.990 BLAST top hit similarity in the INSDs calculated for each supergroup (A) and their MPS frequencies (B).

Fig. 3. Results of the assignment test (bar plot analysis) by Structure [11]

structuring of the 13 samples. In the summer of 2014, 47 and 9 clonal strains were isolated from Oki islands, Shimane Pref. (36°19.61'N, 133°33.93'E) and Yoichi, Hokkaido (43°12.11'N, 140°46.33'E), respectively. To verify the origin of the Yoichi sample, population genetic analysis was performed using 10 microsatellites. To identify the origin of the newly isolated strains in 2014, a Tsushima sample (TSM) as the Sea of Japan populations ($n = 32$), a Yatsushiro Sea sample (YAT) as the Yatsushiro Sea populations ($n = 31$), and a Nagasaki sample (KSM) as the other populations ($n = 31$) were used as the reference source populations [10]. As the result of the assignment test (bar plot analysis) by Structure [11], Oki islands sample was identified as the Sea of Japan population, and Yoichi sample was suggested as the admixture of the Sea of Japan and other populations. However, a large genetic break between these two populations was seen [10]. Unfortunately, a good hydro dynamic model to simulate the current system around the Sea of Japan and Hokkaido is not currently available. We speculate that these two populations, which were forming dense blooms in Korean coastal waters and in Kujukushima (Nagasaki Pref.), were separately transferred from west to east and north by the Tsushima warm current, but mixed before reaching Yoichi.

In this study, our data strongly suggested that these HAB species were transported from the Korean and Kyusyu coastal waters by the Tsushima

warm current in the summer season. In Funka Bay and Okhotsk Sea in Hokkaido, scallop aquaculture is a very popular and important industry. Therefore, we need to continue the time-series monitoring using the MPS-based technology, not only for understanding the biodiversity but also for HAB monitoring to protect the shellfish industry.

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Satoshi Nagai receiving the Research Progress Award from the Japanese Society of Fisheries Science during the Society meeting in 2018.

Quantifying dinoflagellate cysts in bottom sediments: a response to Anderson 2018

Problems associated with quantifying dinoflagellate cysts in bottom sediments featured prominently in Don Anderson's personal retrospective view of his contribution to the early days of HAB cyst research published recently in this newsletter [1]. He correctly recognizes that cysts/g dry weight is the appropriate method for quantifying cysts in core samples as well as in surface sediment samples to be compared with cores for geologically based studies. However, the impression given that his work has been criticized for not using this method for biological studies is in my experience incorrect, and I wish to address this here.

The reference cited by Anderson to my criticism of the "wet method" utilizing cysts/volume wet sediment is incorrect – the correct reference is: *Dale B, 2001. Marine dinoflagellate cysts as indicators of eutrophication and industrial pollution: a discussion* [2]. Readers will see that this criticizes the wet method as inappropriate for a study of cores for eutrophication signals, and my recommendation to standardize methods based on the dry method for such work (on recommendation by one of the referees for this 2001 paper) has been adopted by others in the field ever since. This was not a criticism of biological studies by Anderson or others, nor do I know of such criticism from elsewhere.

However, criticism of some of the biological work investigating cysts in sediments has been expressed at meetings when these studies ignored basic elements of the science of sedimentology, and I believe sedimentation processes should be the main focus of this discussion on quantitative methods. Cysts in sediments have the potential to act as seedbeds for some HAB species, as first pointed out by Karen Steidinger, but the cysts also have to be recognized as just one (often very minor) component of finer-grained particles in a dynamic process of transport and deposition in the broader sedimentary regime. Modelling the role of cysts as seedbeds not

Professor Barrie Dale

only requires an understanding of phytoplankton ecology from the biological sciences (e.g. Dale & Murphy, 2014, [3]), but it also necessitates an understanding of the basic elements of sedimentology developed as an important field in geology.

This is not the place to summarize "Sedimentology 101", but it should suffice to point out that geologists have studied modern sediments extensively, using sophisticated methods to investigate the full range of processes of transport and sedimentation down to the micro-fabric of bottom sediments. The extent to which knowledge of sedimentology is critical for studies of cysts in sediments depends very much on the objectives of the study. For example, our research provides quantitative data of cysts/volume of sediment (i.e. the wet method) to help the Environment Agency, Abu Dhabi, with environmental impact assessments for sediment dredging projects. The objective, in this case, is simply to estimate the numbers of HAB cysts potentially released from sediment dredged by the project, a factor which is not dependent on sediment characteristics. In contrast, attempts to quantitatively model cysts in sediment after the occurrence of a HAB to forecast blooms for the following year (e.g. Anderson and co-workers in the Gulf of Maine) necessitate much more consideration of sedimentology.

The main aspect of sedimentology that has to be considered in attempts

to model a HAB from cysts in sediments is that bottom sediments are a dynamic feature of, rather than a benign end product of a complex sedimentary system.

Dynamics of the sedimentary regime that affect cyst concentrations in bottom sediments

There are areas of quiescent sedimentation where bottom sediments accumulate layer upon layer without disturbance for long periods of time (varved sediments), almost always in deeper marine basins with extremely low oxygen levels that prevents disturbance by benthic organisms (bioturbation). Since low oxygen levels are known to inhibit excystment, these low-oxygen sediments are not likely to be of interest for modelling seed beds. For better oxygenated sediments that may be of interest, two main sedimentological parameters affect cyst concentrations: transport and disturbance, often constantly working together.

Bodies of water do not usually remain still for long periods of time; turbulence from wind, waves and currents affect the water column, and sediment traps suspended at different levels confirm that fine-grained particles including cysts may be transported for long distances from where they enter the system, before reaching bottom sediment. Once on the bottom, fine particles are often subjected to further turbulence and bioturbation that tends to transport and concentrate finer-grained sediment including cysts into deeper parts of the system (seen on sea charts where mud often characterizes the bottom in deeper water while more sandy sediments are found on "higher ground"). When particles reach their point of accumulation they are subject to bioturbation by benthic organisms which, particularly in productive waters, are constantly mixing the sediments – burying new particles and re-suspending older material from deeper sediment. In addition to these natural processes coastal waters are increasingly affected by intensive bottom trawling, and dramatic pictures are emerging from robot cameras that show large areas of seabed crisscrossed with scour-marks from fishing gear that caused massive resuspension and re-sedimentation of bottom sediment. Ob-

viously, sample sites should be chosen to avoid such areas if possible.

Clearly, there is room for questions or criticism when this dynamic system is modelled from the assumption that bottom sediments, for example in Anderson's work in The Gulf of Maine, are in a static stable condition whereby a sample taken in the fall one year is considered representative of the seed bed the following spring. The fall sample may well contain many freshly formed cysts from that summer's bloom, but by next spring these would be expected to be at least partially disseminated into deeper sediment and possibly replaced by some older cysts of more questionable viability by the processes mentioned above. The crucial question for modelers of how many viable cysts germinate from the proposed seed bed to initiate the next bloom will always be difficult/practically impossible to demonstrate. How can one know which cysts from the variety of seed beds in shallower to deeper water, potentially excysting at different times, produce which motiles in the water column in coastal regions with a complex interconnected hydrographic system offering different ecological opportunities? Modelers promising long-term forecasting of HAB from

cysts in sediment should be expected to take account of the basic factors affecting the sediments, and they are obliged to check simple assumptions made about sediments where possible. For example, if modelers of HAB in the Gulf of Maine had calculated cyst concentrations in the postulated "seed bed" closer to the postulated time of excystment in the spring, and checked cyst concentrations again soon after "excystment", they could see if cyst concentrations were reduced by the amounts required to support the excystment rates assumed in the models. One of the often stated justifications for modeling is that it can expose aspects of science needing further study. I hope the modelers will accept the explanations presented here as an example of this: that inadequate consideration of the dynamics in the sedimentary system contributes to the high level of uncertainty in the models.

Behind Anderson's complaint about unjust criticism from geologists lies an important principle that is fundamental to how science progresses: scientists have a responsibility to question/criticize each other's work. This is particularly valuable where different disciplines overlap (in this case biology and geology). Geologists know that water

content varies between sediment samples, and biologists were made aware of this only when they were not accounting for it in their work. There are simple, standard methods for checking water content, and these were eventually employed by biologists to account for this factor – surely a positive response to valuable criticism.

From working with both geological and biological aspects of dinoflagellate cysts, I have benefitted greatly from being exposed to and learning from expertise in both fields. I know that HAB science will only benefit from a better understanding of the dynamics of the sedimentary system.

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HAN contributors follow an honorable tradition of disputation; differences instead of differentials. Figure shows Isaac Newton and Leibniz, protagonists of the most famous intellectual dispute in history.

Contribution of marine invertebrates to Ciguatera poisoning : the case study of French Polynesia

Reported as early as the 15th century by explorers, ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) is the most prominent non-bacterial seafood poisoning worldwide. Widespread in tropical and subtropical regions, CFP results from the consumption of coral reef fish contaminated with ciguatoxins (CTXs) produced by *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* species. These potent neurotoxins can pose a severe health hazard causing gastrointestinal, neurological and cardiovascular disorders, with cold allodynia being a typical symptom of ciguatera.

Yet, other seafood products such as several species of marine invertebrates highly prized by many island communities in the Pacific region, have also been episodically involved in ciguatera-like poisoning incidents. Indeed, the first mass poisoning outbreak ever documented in the literature following the ingestion of the giant clam *Tridacna maxima* occurred in 1964 in Bora Bora Island (French Polynesia). This poisoning event which affected a total of 33 patients who displayed mainly gastrointestinal and neurological disorders, eventually led to the death of 3 people [1]. Years later,

from 2001 onwards, similar incidents were again reported from French Polynesia, but also New Caledonia and the Cook Islands. Of note, besides the digestive and neurological manifestations typically evocative of CFP, patients displayed additional symptoms, such as the rapid onset of the disease, an unusual severity of symptoms including paralysis in some patients, and a rapid burning of their mouth and tongue [2, 3]. Additional poisoning cases following the ingestion of sea urchins, i.e. *Tripneustes esculentus* and *Tripneustes gratilla*, have also been described in the West Indies [4] and French Polynesia [5, 6], respectively, while other marine invertebrates such as the big blue octopus *Octopus scyanea*, the nimble spray crab, *Percnon* spp., and the large worm shell *Dendropoma maxima* have been involved in sporadic poisoning events in the Cook Islands [2]. In addition, the lobsters *Panulirus penicillatus* and octopus from the Republic of Kiribati [7] as well as two starfish from Madeira waters, *Ophidiaster ophidianus* and *Marthasterias glacialis* [8], have been recently found to also bioaccumulate CTXs.

Since many of these edible marine invertebrate species represent a valuable source of protein and revenue in Pacific island countries and territories (PICTs), it is therefore important to document these atypical forms of ciguatera further. The following data describe 2 recent mass-poisoning events which occurred in Anaho Bay (Nuku Hiva Island, Marquesas archipelago, Fig. 1) following the consumption of toxic specimens of *Tectus niloticus*, (gastropods) and *Tripneustes gratilla* (echinoids) in 2014 and 2015, respectively [9-11]. Regardless of the toxic seafood, all patients (9 tourists and 3 tourists, respectively) experienced gastrointestinal and neurological disorders. Cardiovascular symptoms were recorded only in patients that had ingested *T. niloticus*, a likely explanation for this being that patients who consumed toxic sea urchins delayed presenting at hospital, [10, 11]. In the case of the *T. niloticus* poisoning event, the unusual severity of both gastrointestinal and neurological symptoms necessitated the hospitalization of 6 out of the 9 patients.

Unfortunately, in both cases, no food remnants were available for confirmation analysis. Instead, field investigations were undertaken periodically in the toxic area in order to survey the toxicity level in these 2 groups of marine invertebrates and assess the identity

Fig. 1. Study site of Anaho Bay in Nuku Hiva Island, Marquesas Archipelago, French Polynesia

Figure 2. Comparison of Pacific ciguatoxins (P-CTXs) profiles in A) *in vitro* cultures of *Gambierdiscus polynesiensis* (TB-92 [14]), B) *Tectus niloticus* (Nuku Hiva, July 2014 [9]) and C) *Tripneustes gratilla* (Nuku Hiva, July 2015 [11])

of the toxins involved [9, 11]. Toxicity analysis using the neuroblastoma cell based assay (CBA-N2a) and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) revealed the presence of several congeners of P-CTXs in *T. niloticus* and *T. gratilla* toxic samples, at levels consistently above the safety limit recommended for human consumption (0.01 ng P-CTX1B/g of tissue [12]), i.e. 11.47 and 20.19 ng P-CTX3C equiv/g of tissue, respectively. These results suggest that *T. niloticus* and *T. gratilla* are able to naturally bioaccumulate P-CTXs in their tissues [9, 11].

Interestingly, these findings were consistent with *Gambierdiscus* abundance data from Anaho Bay obtained using both the natural (i.e. macroalgae) and the artificial (i.e. window-screens) substrate methods [13]. Enumeration of *Gambierdiscus* cells achieved both microscopically and by way of quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) assays allowed to confirm that *Gambierdiscus* populations were present in this area, while qPCR estimation of the relative distribution of *Gambierdiscus* species in Anaho Bay revealed that *G. polynesiensis* was the dominant species in this toxic area [9, 11]. This species is known to produce P-CTX3C, 3B, 4A, 4B and M-seco-CTX3C as the major CTXs congeners in cultures [14]. The LC-MS/MS analyses performed on *T. niloticus* and *T. gratilla* samples showed that P-CTX3B was the major congener present, followed by P-CTX3C and to a lesser extent, P-CTX4A and P-CTX4B (Fig. 1) [9, 11]. Of note, P-CTX3B is also the major congener found in *Tridacna maxima* experimentally fed *G. polynesiensis* cells [15]. All these observations suggest that

Gambierdiscus is the likely source of the P-CTXs congeners detected in these marine invertebrates. Sea urchins also contained a significant amount of 51-OH-P-CTX3C (Fig. 2), an analog considered to be favored through metabolism in trophic food webs [11].

Additionally, the field-surveys conducted in Anaho Bay at different time periods emphasized the slow depuration rate for CTXs in both *T. niloticus* and *T. gratilla* toxic samples. The mechanisms controlling the uptake, metabolism and depuration of CTXs in CFP-prone marine invertebrate species are still poorly addressed, thus stressing the need for further investigations. Such knowledge will undoubtedly benefit both ciguatera risk management programs and predictive models of CTX accumulation in these organisms.

In conclusion, these recent results provide evidence that a variety of marine invertebrates actually represent a potential bioaccumulation pathway for ciguatera toxins in marine food webs. Considering that most CFP monitoring programs currently rely on the survey of *Gambierdiscus* cell densities and species composition and/or the monitoring of CTXs in fish, these novel findings highlight the importance of also taking into account the toxicity of marine invertebrates whose consumption may pose a prominent health risk for populations in CFP prone areas.

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Solid Phase Adsorption Toxin Tracking (SPATT) technology for field monitoring of *Gambierdiscus* toxins with passive samplers

Ciguatera poisoning is a seafood intoxication classically associated with the consumption of tropical coral reef fish contaminated with ciguatoxins (CTXs), although some marine invertebrates such as bivalves, gastropods or echinoids are also potential vectors of ciguatera [1-3]. CTXs are polyether neurotoxins produced by dinoflagellates of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa*, and are responsible for severe acute digestive, neurological, and cardiovascular symptoms in humans [4]. Ciguatera has major health and economic impacts on vulnerable island communities whose subsistence strongly relies on the sustainable exploitation of marine resources, such as in the Pacific island countries and territories (PICTs) where high incidence rates have been consistently reported in the past two decades [5].

Most surveillance programmes currently rely on the survey of cell densities and species composition of *Gambierdiscus* populations, as well as on the evaluation of CTXs concentrations in marine products. However, such methods are time consuming and expensive, thus emphasizing the need for supplementary tools, based on the spatio-temporally

integrated sampling of dissolved algal toxins directly in marine environments. The SPATT (solid phase adsorption toxin tracking) technology, first introduced in 2004 [6], uses porous synthetic resins capable of adsorbing dissolved toxins directly from the water column (Fig. 1). Numerous laboratory and field studies, testing different adsorbent substrates of which Diaion® HP20 resin appears to be the most versatile substrate, have been carried out worldwide to assess the applicability of these passive monitoring devices to the detection of lipophilic and hydrophilic toxins produced by a variety of marine and freshwater microorganisms [7]. Regarding the monitoring of toxins associated with ciguatera, one laboratory study has demonstrated the efficacy of HP20 resin for the detection of dissolved CTXs and maitotoxins (MTXs) in *Gambierdiscus* cultures [8].

The efficacy of SPATT technology to detect *Gambierdiscus* toxins in the field in ciguateric biotopes was recently confirmed by the deployment of SPATT devices filled with 10 g of HP20 resin for 48 h in two French Polynesian sites: main village of Kaukura Island (Tuamotu archipelago) and Anaho Bay in Nuku Hiva Island (Marquesas archipelago),

characterized by a moderate vs. high risk of ciguatera [9]. The presence of CTXs in SPATT devices was assessed using the neuroblastoma cell-based assay (CBA-N2a) and results showed that SPATT devices deployed in Anaho Bay were able to retain 1.30 ± 0.41 ng P-CTX3C equiv. g^{-1} HP20 resin. Liquid chromatography - tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) analyses confirmed that P-CTX3B and P-CTX3C were primarily retained on SPATT devices. These results are coherent with environmental observations that confirmed the presence of significant amounts of *Gambierdiscus* cells in Anaho Bay, most notably in the species *G. polynesiensis* known for its very high toxic potential, and with toxicological analyses that demonstrated the presence of CTXs in all marine products tested [2,3]. In contrast, no CTXs were detected in SPATT devices deployed in Kaukura Island. However, as with SPATT devices deployed in Anaho Bay, LC-MS/MS analyses revealed the adsorption of a putative MTX analogue, known as MTX3, on SPATT devices deployed in Kaukura Island. Recent studies indicate that putative MTX3 is ubiquitous within *Gambierdiscus* genus [10], suggesting its potential use as a biomarker of the occurrence of *Gambierdiscus* cells in the natural environment. Since a very low density of *Gambierdiscus* cells was observed in Kaukura Island, the detection of putative MTX3 but not of CTXs on SPATT devices suggest either the presence of non-toxic *Gambierdiscus*

Fig. 1. Example of a design of SPATT device assembly and field deployment. Left and middle: the SPATT device is made of two nylon mesh layers with a porous synthetic resin (Diaion® HP20, polystyrene-divinylbenzene matrix, is the most used resin), and fixed between two PVC circular frames. Right: in the field, the SPATT device is inserted in plastic grids to prevent its damage and grazing by fish, and maintained in a vertical position in the water column using weights and floats. © M. Roué (modified from [7] and [9])

Fig. 2. Summary of the results demonstrating that SPATT passive sampling could advantageously contribute to the reinforcement of ciguateric risk assessment and management programmes as a supplementary tool.

or of very low densities of toxic *Gambierdiscus* cells. However, CTXs were detected in numerous fish collected in Kaukura Island (CBA-N2a), suggesting that blooms of toxic *Gambierdiscus* had previously occurred in this area, leading to the bioaccumulation of CTXs in marine products, but had disappeared at the time of the SPATT devices deployment. Another explanation could be that SPATT devices allow for the detection of CTXs in the field only when high levels of CTXs are dissolved in the seawater and are thus relevant only in highly ciguateric locations.

In all cases, these results (summarized in Fig. 2) confirmed the ability of SPATT technology to detect CTXs in the field and thus emphasize the relevance of this toxin-based technique as a useful supplementary tool when assessing the risks associated with *Gambierdiscus* proliferation in locations highly prone to ciguatera. It should be highlighted that SPATT devices are only able to give indications of the presence of *Gambierdiscus* cells (detection of MTX3) and their toxicity (detection of CTXs) in an area at a given time, but they are not effective to guarantee the edibility of

marine products that could have bio-accumulated toxins in their tissues. The simplicity, low-cost and logistical advantages (e.g. storage and transport) offered by these easy-to-use devices make SPATT technology a valuable tool well adapted to the survey of CFP risk, most notably in widely dispersed and remote sampling locations in PICTs. Moreover, given the risk of simultaneous accumulation of multiple biotoxins in seafood products in tropical environments, the use of SPATT technology, when combined with downstream analyses such as LC-MS/MS multi-toxin screenings, also offers promising prospects in the framework of emerging toxins surveillance.

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New limits of *Ostreopsis* distribution in the Bay of Biscay: a first report of *Ostreopsis* in Santander Bay, Cantabria (Northern Spain)

Fig. 1. Location of sampling sites

The genus *Ostreopsis* encompasses benthic dinoflagellates that represent one of the main microalgal threats for beach tourism in warm-temperate waters. Blooms of species within this genus can produce toxins, mostly belonging to the palytoxin group [1], which may cause problems affecting the respiratory system and/or skin irritation, due to their association with toxic marine aerosols. Not all the *Ostreopsis* species have been confirmed as toxin producers with only 4 out of the currently 11 species described considered toxic [2].

Ostreopsis proliferates forming a thin pellicle on the rocks or on macrophytes, but it is possible to also find it in the water column detached from the substrate forming aggregates, usually after very hydrodynamic episodes. The distribution of this genus has been typically restricted to tropical and temperate waters. In the last years, reports of *Ostreopsis* blooms in temperate waters

have increased, some of them occurring in places where they had not been observed before [3]. Such is the case of the Bay of Biscay, where *Ostreopsis* spp. were recurrently observed in the southeastern part of the Bay in studies conducted during 2010 and 2011 [4]. In those surveys, the western limit of *Ostreopsis* distribution was established at the locality of Santoña [4].

Santander Bay is the largest estuary in Northern Spain, with important commercial, fishing and tourist activities. On September 7th, 2017, *Ostreopsis* was recorded for the first time west of Santoña from a survey performed in Loredo Beach, at the mouth of the Bay, (Fig. 1). Two weeks later, on September 21st, samples from two sites to the west of Santander Bay, Llanes and San Vicente de la Barquera, were collected to establish the new limits of *Ostreopsis*. No cells of this genus were detected. Additional samples close to Santoña

confirmed the presence of *Ostreopsis* in this location. Up to date, Santander Bay represents the new western limit of *Ostreopsis* distribution in the Bay of Biscay. Considering the socio-economic importance of Santander Bay, the presence of *Ostreopsis* in the area should be regularly monitored.

Cultures of *Ostreopsis* isolated from epiphytic cells on macroalgae at the sampling stations in Santander Bay and Santoña were analyzed genetically to identify the species. The amplification of the ITS1 rDNA region performed with specific primers [5] confirmed that the strains belong to *Ostreopsis siamensis*, corroborating our first suspicion based on the cells' morphology (Fig. 2). These strains are currently kept at the Microalgae Culture Collection of the University of the Basque Country.

Temperatures close to the sampling site, in the mouth of Santander Bay, were above 19 °C from mid June until the end of September 2017. Our observations agree with the hypothesis posed by David *et al* [4], that temperatures above 19.5 °C during at least three consecutive months are necessary for the populations of *Ostreopsis* to develop in the Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula.

Additional surveys should be planned, both to the north and west of Santander Bay, to definitively assess the distribution of *Ostreopsis siamensis* in the Bay of Biscay.

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Fig. 2. *Ostreopsis siamensis* from Santander Bay

Bloom of *Ostreopsis* cf. *siamensis* in Lisbon Bay

Fig. 1. Sampling sites on Lisbon Bay

Reports of benthic HAB events have increased during the last decade in temperate regions. These have been associated with proliferations of benthic toxic dinoflagellates, in particular species of *Ostreopsis*. The Mediterranean coast of the Iberian Peninsula has been regularly affected by blooms of the highly toxic species *O. cf. ovata* [1]. This species produces potent toxins of the palytoxin group and has been responsible for several outbreaks leading to mortality of marine organisms, human health problems and economic losses due to beach closures in tourist areas [2]. A bloom of *O. cf. ovata* was recorded in 2011 at Dona Ana Beach, Lagos, one of the most picturesque tourist beaches on the Algarve coast in Portugal, with no significant harmful effects [3]. So far, this is the only area on the Atlantic coast of Iberia where *O. cf. ovata* has been reported [3, 4]. A second *Ostreopsis* species, *O. cf. siamensis*, is also present in the Mediterranean and on the Atlantic Iberian coast. *O. cf. siamensis* has a more restricted distribution than *O. cf. ovata* in the Mediterranean but the opposite is observed on the Atlantic coast: whilst *O. cf. ovata* is only known to be present in the south of Portugal, *O. cf. siamensis* has a wide, albeit fragmented, distribution from southern Portugal to the Bay of Biscay [5].

Sampling in Lisbon Bay during summer-early autumn has been carried out every year since 2001, and cells of *O. cf. siamensis* regularly found, both in the benthos and in the water column, although in very low densities.

In September 2017, a survey was carried out to study the benthic dinoflagellate community in Lisbon Bay. The area is characterized by a succession of sandy and rocky beaches and sampling was carried out in intertidal pools. During the sampling of the first site (Fig. 1, G), the presence of mucilaginous threads in several of the tide pools was immediately observed (Fig. 2). A thin yellow/brownish pellicle covered the substrate, dominated by small,

mostly finely branched and foliose thalli, forming a diverse cespitose assemblage; specimens of *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Codium* sp., and *Halopteris scoparia*, among others, were also present (Table 1). Samples of representative macroalgae from the tide pools with surrounding water were collected by hand with plastic bags, vigorously shaken for 1 minute to detach the epiphytic community, and the resulting water samples stored in bottles after sieving through a 100- μ m net. The macroalgae were kept in the plastic bags for fresh (FW) and dry weight (DW) determination. To estimate cell densities in the water column, water samples were also collected in plastic containers and fixed with 2% neutral Lugol's solution. Fresh sample was used for observation, single-cell isolation and establishment of monoclonal cultures. The epiphytic community was immediately checked under the microscope, and the occurrence of an *Ostreopsis* sp. bloom was confirmed (Fig. 2).

Following these observations, samples were collected the next day at 11 sites along an east-west transect (Fig. 1) to study the geographical extension of the proliferation. Samples were collected and processed as above. Living cells

Fig. 2. Top left: mucilaginous brown filaments in a water pool. Top right: *Ostreopsis* cells under the optical microscope; Bottom: Station G in the Bay of Lisbon.

Table 1 - List of the macroalgae community species

<i>Asparagopsis armata</i>	<i>Corallina</i> sp.
<i>Caulacanthus ustulatus</i>	<i>Cystoseira</i> sp.
Ceramiales	<i>Derbesia</i> sp.
<i>Ceramium</i> spp.	<i>Dictyota dichotoma</i>
<i>Champia</i> sp.	<i>Gelidium pusillum</i>
<i>Champia parvula</i>	<i>Gracilaria foliifera</i>
<i>Cladostephus spongiosus</i>	<i>Halopteris scoparia</i>
<i>Codium tomentosum</i>	Rhodomelaceae
<i>Colpomenia</i> sp.	<i>Ulva</i> spp.

were isolated under the microscope, using a glass micropipette and placed into wells of a 24-multiwell plate with 1 mL of filtered seawater enriched with f/20-Si medium, kept under a 12:12 L/D cycle.

Ostreopsis spp. density (cells L⁻¹) in the water column was estimated using the Utermöhl method and that of epiphytic cells with a Sedgwick-Rafter chamber, and results expressed as cells g⁻¹ FW and cells g⁻¹ DW of macroalgae. For the macroalgae DW estimates, samples were dried for at least 24 hours at 60°C. Five strains were established in culture and are kept in the Algal Culture Collection of the University of Lisbon (ALISU). As *Ostreopsis* spp. are known to be cryptic species, molecular analyses were performed for species identification. About 30 mL of each culture were centrifuged, and the rDNA from the pellet was extracted, amplified and sequenced. Amplification of the ITS1-5.8S-ITS2 rDNA was performed with

ITSA and ITSB primers [6]. Phylogenetic analysis (not shown) revealed that all the studied sequences grouped in the *Ostreopsis* cf. *siamensis* clade. The highest cell density, 1.04 x 10⁵ cells g⁻¹ DW (3.4 x 10⁴ cells g⁻¹ FW) was found at station G. The geographical distribution of the samples identifies this site as a hotspot, with densities of *O. cf. siamensis* decreasing to the east and west of

station G (Fig. 3). The cell density in the water column at this site was 2.1 x 10³ cells L⁻¹.

The densities reported here are low compared with those reported for *O. cf. ovata* in the Mediterranean Sea (5.3 x 10⁴ cells L⁻¹ [7]; 6.8 x 10⁴ cells L⁻¹ [8]; 8.54 x 10⁶ cells g⁻¹ FW [8]; 1.3 x 10⁶ cells g⁻¹ FW and 1.6 x 10⁷ cells g⁻¹ DW [9]). However, reports of *Ostreopsis* cf. *siamensis* blooms in the Atlantic and Mediterranean are rare. To our knowledge, only two reports have been published before: one from the Atlantic coast of Morocco (3.7 x 10³ - 10⁵ cells L⁻¹) [10] and the other from Tunisia (3.75 x 10⁴ cells L⁻¹) in the Mediterranean [11]. Work on the toxicity of *O. cf. siamensis* has shown nearly undetectable levels of palytoxin per cell [12], thus the species represents a low risk for the environment and human health. These findings suggest that blooms may go unnoticed due to the lack of apparent harmful effects. *O. cf. siamensis* was first detected

on the West coast of Iberia in 2008 [13] and has since been regularly detected at very low concentrations. In the present work, we report for the first time, bloom densities of an *Ostreopsis* species on the West coast of Iberia. This raises questions regarding the environmental conditions that may trigger these blooms and how these may be related to the present trend of ocean warming. Very little is known on the ecology of *O. cf. siamensis* and more work is needed to better understand the distribution and bloom dynamics of this species in temperate waters.

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Fig. 3. Densities of epiphytic *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* cells in grams per dry weight.

A possible link between the breakdown of a fertilizer tank and a toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* bloom

Fig. 1. Map of Denmark with approximate locations of the respective mussel harvesting areas (63, 66, 68, 71), Fredericia (the origin of the fertilizer outlet) and Horsens. Credit: openstreet-map.org

In March and April 2016, a major bloom of toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* (PN) caused an extensive closure of mussel harvesting areas in Denmark due to raised levels of domoic acid (DA). Areas close to the east coast of Jutland (Denmark) were heavily affected by the bloom and several productive shellfish areas where closed for up to five weeks. Cell concentrations and the PN proportion of the total planktonic community were relatively low at the time. What caused the high toxicity?

DA is a potent neurotoxin that bioaccumulates as shellfish and copepods vector the toxin up the food web. Hereby DA can potentially cause problems with intoxication of consumers such as fish, birds, and mammals. The toxin is known to cause Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) in humans. Intoxication of humans is usually avoided due to the existence of monitoring and testing programs of commercially harvested bivalves worldwide. No human intoxication was reported during the spring

bloom in Denmark in 2016. Harvest of blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*) by the industry in the affected areas was closed as soon as toxin was detected in mussel meat and the mussels already harvested were discarded. The areas concerned are usually very productive and the closure resulted in a weekly lost revenue of >100.000 DKK to local fishermen. The fishery was reopened after 4-5 weeks, under intensified surveillance.

The bloom probably originated north-east of Horsens Fjord (Fig. 1). The first measurements of DA in mussel samples were detected on March 7,

2016. During the following weeks, DA was detected in adjacent areas along the east coast of Jutland. Toxic PN blooms are rare in Denmark but these specific areas have previously been affected [1]. Other areas of Danish coastal waters might likewise be subject to DA accumulation but toxin levels are only measured in areas subject to mussel

fishery, leaving toxic blooms undetected in other areas.

By the time of the bloom, the diatom community primarily consisted of *P. seriata* (Fig. 3). Identification of *P. seriata* as the potential culprit diatom for the toxicity was confirmed by TEM (Fig. 2). *P. seriata* as the responsible diatom was not surprising, as it has previously formed highly toxic blooms in the area [1]. The cell concentration peaked at the beginning of the bloom at 110,800 cells L⁻¹ (Fig. 1), while the toxin content in mussel meat peaked two weeks later with 47 mg DA kg⁻¹ of mussel meat. This is a relatively high amount of toxin, considering the low cell concentration.

The reason for the two-weeks temporal difference between DA peaks and peaks in cell numbers might be due to the sampling procedure, with irregular sampling and water samples for phytoplankton monitoring being gathered on other days than samples for toxin analyses of shellfish flesh. *P. seriata* is known for its ability to produce high amounts of DA given the appropriate environmental conditions. Several physical-chemical factors are known to induce DA production in PN. Silicate limitation, light and temperature are well documented as DA inducing factors for *P. seriata*, and presence of copepod grazers is a newly discovered potent inducing factor for DA production [2].

On February 3rd 2016, approximately one month prior to the bloom, large amounts of liquid nitrogen fertilizer were spilled into the environment as a result of the breakdown of a fertilizer storage silo located on the harbour of Fredericia. The magnitude of this discharge was arguably around 4000

Fig. 2. Concentrations of *P. seriata* cells in the water column and of domoic acid content in fresh mussel meat during spring 2016 in four different areas along the east coast of Jutland.

Fig. 3. *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* TEM micrograph of the poroid structure arranged within the striae consisting of two outer rows of larger poroids and one or two inner rows of smaller poroids.

Fig. 4. TEM micrograph of a mixed water sample from the bloom, resembling a culture sample.

tons. The silo contained 9500 tons at the time of the breakdown and thereby passed its maximum capacity by 500 tons [3]. The adjacent areas and especially the waters immediately outside the harbour were heavily affected by the extensive amounts of nitrogen. The discharge consisted of N32 and N16 fertilizer liquids, which is predominantly urea. Organic nitrogen in the form of urea is (as inorganic nitrogen) 100 % bioavailable [4]. The organic molecule in urea is easily separated from the rest by the enzyme urease, splitting ammonium from bicarbonate [5] [6]. Monitoring data showed peaks in nitrate levels immediately after the outlet, revealing more than double the average amount of available nitrate for the area. Phosphorus levels were not increased.

In Denmark, the major part of nitrogen runoff from land happens from October till January. During this period

algal growth is limited by light rather than nutrients. From February and further into the summer period, algal growth is controlled mostly by nutrients. The usual pattern is depletion of phosphorous followed by nitrogen depletion.

In spring 2016 in Little Belt (between Jutland and Funen) the discharge of 4000 tons of readily available nitrogen must inarguably have affected the ecosystem in the area. The general concentrations of planktonic algae were unusually high in the following month (data not shown here). Available nitrogen was possibly crucial for *P. seriata* to overtake the diatom community for a period of time and additionally producing the high amounts of DA vectoring up the food web.

Nitrogen repletion has been shown to induce toxin production in other PN species. Different forms of nitrogen can

induce DA production in *P. australis* [7], and the most potent DA-inducing N form has been shown to be urea. It is very likely that urea and/or nitrate affected the DA production in *P. seriata*. Studies on *P. australis* show that urea is highly potent and induces the production of DA at least 4-fold compared to nitrate and ammonium treatments. Ammonium doubled the production of DA compared to the control (normal sea levels of nutrients)[7].

Our observations support the hypothesis that high N levels induce DA production in PN. An increase in land-based runoff of N (especially in the form of urea) may increase the frequency and toxicity of toxic blooms. Therefore strict limits of fertilizer usage and spills may be important to avoid washout and runoff of N, potentially causing algal blooms, damaging the environment and mussel harvesting industries.

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Golden alga *Prymnesium parvum* Carter bloom off Azhikode, southwest India

In September 2009, during the southwest monsoon season, a quasi-mono-specific bloom of *Prymnesium parvum* was collected off Azhikode (10° 11' 02" N; 76° 09' 22" E), on the southwest coast of India (Fig. 1). A conspicuous pale brownish surface water discoloration extended through an area about 8-10 nautical miles off the coast. The bloom did not result in foam production or fish mortality and lasted only one day as heavy rain dissipated the cells. This may be the first report of a *P. parvum* bloom from Indian waters (Fig. 2) [1].

At the time of the bloom, a cell maximum of 8×10^7 cells L⁻¹ and chlorophyll *a* and carotenoid concentrations of 13.54 µg L⁻¹ and 1.91 µg L⁻¹ respectively were observed. The sea surface temperature was 28°C, salinity 34 psu and pH 8. Nutrient concentrations in the bloom area, determined with standard methods [1] were: total nitrogen 12.6 µmol L⁻¹, phosphate 1.9 µmol L⁻¹, silicate 62 µmol L⁻¹ and dissolved oxygen, 1.41 mg L⁻¹.

Blooms of *P. parvum* associated with faunal mortalities are quite common in temperate seas. Cell densities of 5×10^7 cells L⁻¹ have been associated with faunal loss [2]. However, in the present bloom event, no fish mortalities were recorded despite the high cell density observed.

In addition to strain variability of *P. parvum* from different geographic areas, nutrients may have played a significant role in the harmless effect of this *P. parvum* bloom. The toxicity of *Prymnesium* is known to increase remarkably under nitrogen and phosphorous stress [3]. Salinity is another factor regulating the toxicity in *Prymnesium*: most toxic

blooms of *P. parvum* have been associated with low salinity (3-12.4 psu) conditions, but in the present study, salinity was 34. The factors responsible for the bloom development have yet to be identified. Hence, it could be concluded that, rather than a single factor, multiple environmental conditions, such as temperature, salinity, pH, nutrients, in addition to geographical adaptations, in a favorable range for a particular species, commonly referred to as species-specific adaptations, played a significant role in the development of the bloom event described here.

The bloom forming microalgae *P. parvum* was isolated and cultures successfully established in the Marine Botany Lab, Dept. of Marine Biology, Microbiology & Biochemistry, Cochin University of Science and Technology, to carry out physiological and toxicological studies. Semi-continuous cultures of *P. parvum* were grown in seawater enriched with Walne's medium at a temperature of 22±2°C, salinity

35psu, pH 8 and an irradiance of 900 lux. The allelopathic effect of *P. parvum* grown in different nutrient conditions (both nutrient sufficient and deficient) was checked against four selected microalgae. Our first results showed that phosphorous limited cultures inhibited growth in cultures of microalgae *Tetraselmis gracilis*, *Chaetoceros calcitrans*, *Nanochloropsis salina* and *Isochrysis galbana* (in prep.).

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Fig. 2. Micrograph of *Prymnesium parvum* established in culture

Regional Workshop on Monitoring and Management Strategies for Benthic HABs

In the last decades, important advances in the prevention of the adverse impacts of harmful algal blooms (HABs) have been achieved by surveillance programs that monitor HAB species in the environment as well as toxins in seafood and associated human diseases. Currently, strategies are well defined with specific guidelines to monitor harmful phytoplankton species and control their synthesized biotoxins in marine products and freshwater reservoirs. However, the situation is very different for benthic HAB (BHABs) microalgae such as species belonging to the dinoflagellate genera *Gambierdiscus*, associated with ciguatera fish poisoning, and *Ostreopsis*, whose blooms constitute a potential emergent threat especially in the Mediterranean. CFP remains today the most common non-bacterial food poisoning globally with Small Island Developing States (SIDS) being the most vulnerable. Changes in climate may exacerbate the impacts.

With the objective to identify the main gaps that limit monitoring of BHAB species and their toxins in the most affected areas and define the best approaches to prevent and manage their impacts, a workshop was held during the Monaco's Ocean Week 9-12 April 2018, at the Oceanographic Museum of Monaco. The workshop focused on three major topics: benthic species surveillance, monitoring of toxins in marine resources and, seafood and epidemiology.

The workshop was organized by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA, www.iaea.org) in partnership with RAMOGE (www.ramoge.org), IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB (www.globalhab.info) and NOAA. It was attended by more than 60 participants including scientists and coastal managers from more than 30 countries joining IAEA Technical Cooperation projects from Asia-Pacific (RAS7026), Africa (RAF7014), Latin America and the Caribbean (RLA7022).

Participants and experts attended from Algeria, Bangladesh, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, El Salvador, Fiji, France, Guatemala, Indonesia, Italy, Kuwait, Malaysia, Marshall Island, Mauritius, Mexico, Monaco, Nicaragua, Pakistan, Panama, Philippines, Seychelles, Spain, Thailand, Tunisia, United-States, Uruguay, Venezuela, Viet Nam, and from United Nation organizations FAO and WHO (Fig 1).

Before the meeting, surveys were distributed to the participants, to identify the main gaps as well as available tools in their own regions. The outcomes of this survey were used to structure group exercises introduced by experts' lectures. Furthermore, a practical demonstration and analysis of different sampling methods for benthic microalgae were provided. Altogether, the workshop contributed to improve the skills of the participants in establishing a need-based monitoring program for toxic BHABs, in a risk assessment perspective. As a continuation of the workshop a sampling method intercomparison exercise was designed. Artificial substrate kits were distributed among participants to conduct sampling in their areas in parallel to sampling natural substrates (macroalgae). The results will help inform sampling methods and

if possible, establish tools for standardized procedures. The exercise is open to the entire international community. The goal of achieving improved assessments of the risks associated with BHABs will help reduce the health, societal and economic impacts, promote sustainable safe seafood, contributing to the achievement of United Nations sustainable development goals (SDGs) worldwide.

For more information or for those interested in participating in the sampling exercise, contact Yasmine Bottein (M-Y.Bottein@iaea.org) and Rodolphe Lemée (rodolphe.lemee@obs-vlfr.fr)

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Fig. 1. Participants in the Regional Workshop on Monitoring and Management Strategies for Benthic HABs, Monaco, 9-12 April 2018

Workshop on morpho-molecular methods for the study of dinoflagellate cysts

A workshop on techniques for the morphological and molecular identification of cysts from toxic HAB species, led by Drs Kenneth Neil Mertens, Kirsty Smith, Lesley Rhodes and Lincoln MacKenzie, was held recently at the Cawthron Institute in Nelson, New Zealand, 12-14 February 2018. This workshop was supported by the Catalyst:Seeding programme, financed by the Royal Society of New Zealand to establish a new research collaboration between Cawthron and IFREMER (Concarneau, France). Twenty-four researchers participated, with the majority from New Zealand and Australia, but also included people from France, Belgium, Singapore, Ireland, the UK and Canada (Fig1). Due to heavy rains on February 11th, several airplanes had trouble in landing at Nelson and experienced delays, but luckily nearly all participants arrived on time for the start of the workshop.

The workshop started on 12 February with a Māori welcoming ceremony (pōwhiri), which included a speech by Cawthron's CEO Charles Eason and a response by Kenneth (IFREMER) in his Dutch native tongue. The speeches were followed by the singing of traditional Māori songs – most memorable was the impressive falsetto of Dave Clark (Marine Institute, Ireland). The ceremony ended with the hongi (a traditional Māori greeting) – all in all quite a spiritual experience indeed. After getting our feet back on earth, the workshop aims were introduced by Kirsty (Cawthron) and Kenneth, after which participants introduced themselves and their specific research topics, which covered several research fields. Geological applications of cysts were exemplified by Anna Pienkowski, Vera Pospelova, Erica Crouch and Lucia Roncaglia – biological applications by Chris Reid, Gustaaf Hallegraeff, Janet Adamson, Aye Aye Mon, Shereen Lim, Viliami Langi and Tony Bui, and molecular tools by Dave Clarke, Rendy Ruvindy, Henna Savela, Laura Biessy and Xavier Pochon. Cawthron MSc students Enora Jaffrézic, Mailys Picard and Julie Steyen also outlined their research projects on HAB species and cysts. After lunch, morphological tech-

niques for cyst study were explained by Kenneth, and were followed by Vera Pospelova (University of Victoria, Canada) who detailed the application of sediment-traps to study cyst production. Thereafter, Lesley and Kirsty presented molecular techniques used for study of motile stages and cysts. Erica Crouch (GNS, New Zealand) outlined paleontological techniques used for late Quaternary paleocological reconstructions around New Zealand, highlighting the work of her collaborator Joe Prebble. After coffee, Lincoln shared with us how blooms of *Alexandrium pacificum* in New Zealand can be traced using both plankton samples as well as sediment samples. Gustaaf Hallegraeff (University of Tasmania, Australia) emphasized how selective the fossil record is, and highlighted new possibilities using modern molecular techniques. Last but not least, Susie Wood (Cawthron) presented her planned research to study the historical evolution of cyanobacterial and other microbial communities in over 300 lakes across New Zealand. The day ended with a delightful dinner at the Indian Café, where a moderate amount of craft beer was consumed.

The next day included practical demonstrations of both morphological as well as molecular methods (Fig. 2). Lincoln demonstrated the use of primuline staining to enumerate *Alexandrium* cysts in the sediment [1]. Kenneth applied the sodium polytungstate method to isolate living cysts from the sediments for germination experiments [2] and the use of the fluorescent dye Solophenyl Flavine 7GFE500 which

avoids fading of fluorescence [3]. The Cawthron laboratories were visited by the participants as well, which were guided by Kirsty and Tim Harwood – everyone was stunned to see the mass production of toxins produced by *Alexandrium pacificum*. After lunch, Kirsty led a hands-on demonstration of three different quantitative PCR experiments that focused on *Alexandrium* and *Azadinium* – the eagerly awaited results showed that everybody did a great job – A for effort! The day ended with a round table discussion about morphological and molecular methods, and highlighted how both methods could be combined, as well with toxin analysis.

After the workshop, several people stayed to visit the Abel Tasman National Park. A water-taxi sped us past fur seals and a rock allegedly split in two by Chuck Norris, to the start of a 12 km hike. The hike was most delightful with impressive views of Tasman Bay even at high temperatures of 27°C, suppressed by tree fern shade along the way. Some pukekos and wekas could be observed, and it was easy to find sand dollars on the beach.

References

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2. Bolch CJS 1997. *Phycologia* 36: 472-478
3. Chomérat N et al 2016. *Phycologia* 56: 193-203

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Fig. 1. Group photo of participants.

Cawthron Summer Scholar Explores Bloom-Forming Freshwater Cyanobacteria

Globally, cyanobacteria blooms in freshwater environments are causing water quality problems and health risks with increasing frequency. New Zealand is no stranger to this, suffering from blooms of toxin-producing cyanobacteria in our lakes (e.g., *Microcystis*) and our rivers (e.g., *Phormidium*). Over the last four decades, this has led to numerous animal deaths (dogs, sheep and cattle) and the closure of recreational swimming sites due to the human risk at certain times of the year. Whilst many advancements in our understanding of cyanobacteria blooms have been made in the past 30-40 years, there are still knowledge gaps surrounding the ecology of bloom-forming cyanobacteria, the triggers for toxin production and risk posed by cyanobacteria blooms in rivers.

Over the summer of 2017/18 the Cawthron Foundation provided the Sir Theodore Rigg scholarship to an undergraduate student to work on research projects associated with bloom-forming cyanobacteria. The scholarship was awarded to Charlotte Tomlinson, a third-year Environmental Science student from the University of Waikato (Hamilton, New Zealand; Fig. 1). Charlotte spent ten weeks at Cawthron Institute working alongside researchers Jonathan Puddick, Konstanze Steiner

and Susie Wood on projects related to freshwater cyanobacteria.

Charlotte's enthusiasm and aptitude meant that she worked on three research projects during her scholarship period. For her primary project, Charlotte purified toxic and non-toxic metabolites from cyanobacteria in order to assess how the compounds influenced the growth and photosynthetic activity of non-toxic cyanobacteria from the Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Micro-algae (CICCM; <http://cultures.cawthron.org.nz/>).

The occurrence of a toxic bloom of *Phormidium* in the Hutt River (Wellington, New Zealand) led to Charlotte taking on a field study to assess whether anatoxins (produced by *Phormidium*) were released into the water and whether any patterns were evident. Going out into the field gave Charlotte a great insight into the diverse range of skills of algal researchers and an appreciation for the importance of work on toxic algae: "There were quite a few people that were interested in what we were doing and the risks posed by toxic algae in the river. "We also noticed a lot of people using the river recreationally, so it is really important to monitor and study what's going on, so that we can help to make it safer for people to use," Charlotte said in a radio inter-

view she took part in during her time at Cawthron (<https://soundcloud.com/cawthroninstitute/kendall-morman-and-charlotte-tomlinson-cawthron-foundation-scholarships>).

Charlotte's third project was a cyanobacteria culturing experiment to evaluate the effect of temperature and light intensity on homoanatoxin-a (HTX) production in *Oscillatoria* strains from the Pasteur Culture Collection of Cyanobacteria (<https://webext.pasteur.fr/cyanobacteria/>). Because one of the *Oscillatoria* strains grew as benthic mats, this meant that 372 individual culturing pottles needed to be prepared, harvested and processed to conduct the experiment under six different culturing conditions. The results from this work have since been used to optimise the production of HTX in the hopes of purifying sufficient quantities for future toxicology work.

Overall, it was a very rewarding experience for all involved in the 2017/18 Cawthron Foundation Summer Scholarship Programme. For the researchers, it provided an opportunity to pass on some of their skills to the next generation of scientists and to inspire them to consider some of the environmental challenges the world faces. Charlotte noted that one of her highlights was being a part of an active science organisation, finding out what other people were working on and assisting others with their research projects.

Acknowledgements

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Fig. 1. Charlotte Tomlinson (Cawthron Foundation Summer Scholar) purifying cyanobacterial toxins for future toxicology work.

Canadian HAB Scientists Hold Workshop to Establish National Priorities and Develop Research Network

A National Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) workshop was organized and chaired by Dr. Ian Perry at the Institute of Ocean Sciences (IOS), Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO), Sidney, British Columbia, July 11-13, 2017. Sixteen workshop participants, representing DFO scientists as well as invited experts from the United States and Canada, discussed Canadian HAB priorities and the development of a network for HAB research in Canada.

Global and national events, including large HAB-related fish kills, HAB impacts on marine mammals and unprecedented domoic-acid-producing HAB events on the Pacific coast, have brought this issue forward as a national research priority. Specific concerns in Canadian marine waters were highlighted, including the impact of HABs as an ecosystem stressor and the negative consequences of HAB events caused by their phycotoxin production and its accumulation in shellfish and the food web. Little is known about HABs in Arctic and sub-Arctic regions of Canada, where climate change is expanding potential areas for such blooms. A concern was noted that low temperatures could result in slow phycotoxin depuration

rates in several bivalve species, and this in turn could lead to toxin accumulations and impacts beyond single events. Other particularly vulnerable areas include Marine Protected Areas and aquaculture sites.

Priorities for workshop participants were to expand existing work and strengthen connections to related programs, such as environmental monitoring and invasive species studies, to provide more HAB information for Canada. The potential for linkages between Canadian interests and the priorities of international networks, such as ICES-IOC WGHABD, IOC IPHAB and Global HAB, was also discussed.

A recommendation from workshop participants was to produce a formal CSAS (Canadian Science Advisory Secretariat) research document and review to assess the status of knowledge in Canada, identify knowledge gaps and highlight areas of particular concern for current and future impacts of HABs on ecosystems and resources. The Science Advice on impact of marine HABs on the Canadian ecosystem is scheduled for early 2019.

Membership of the Canadian HAB Working Group (CAN HAB) is currently

composed of the workshop participants who have a broad range of expertise including taxonomy, genomic, modelling and remote sensing. However, it is hoped that the network will expand to include additional academic, federal and provincial researchers and managers interested in HAB issues in Canada. The Chair of CAN HAB is Cynthia McKenzie (Cynthia.mckenzie@dfo-mpo.gc.ca), a research scientist with DFO based in St. John's, Newfoundland and Labrador. She is the point of contact for more information on this HAB network.

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Fig. 1. Working Group meeting participants (from left to right): Andrea Locke, Ian Perry, Jennifer Martin, Nicky Haigh, Christine Michel, Emmanuel Devred, Luc Comeau, Vera Trainer, Charlie Trick, Cynthia McKenzie, Caroline Longtin, Amy Tabata, Angelica Pena, Bill Cochlan, Michael Scarratt. Participating by telephone: Elysha Gordon. Members of the working group also include Stephen Bates, Michel Starr and Chris Pearce.

Joint FAO, IAEA, IOC and WHO Technical Meeting for the development of an Inter-Agency Global Ciguatera Strategy

Harmful Algae News has previously brought information on an initiative between the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) Environment Laboratories in Monaco jointly with the Oceanographic Commission (IOC), the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO), to coordinate efforts on Ciguatera. To advance the initiative an inter-agency meeting was organized back to back with an IAEA Technical Cooperation Workshop on Monitoring and Management Strategies for Benthic HABs (see separate article in this issue of HAN).

The four agencies met at the IAEA Environment Laboratories, Monaco from April 12-13, 2018 to define key steps to develop and formalize a coordinated strategy to address ciguatera poisoning globally. The strategy covers the following elements: (a) Improving toxic organism detection, monitoring and risk forecasting; (b) Improving toxin detection in the environment and food; and (c) Improving outbreak data collection and human health risk assessments.

The formalized inter-agency agreement will signal to Member States and the user community that the agencies cooperate and thereby raise the awareness on Ciguatera Poisoning and that it also at national level requires interaction and collaboration between different authorities and stakeholders to protect public health and trade against Ciguatera.

We will inform on development of concrete activities in coming issues of Harmful Algae News.

Marie-Yasmine Dechraoui Bottein (IAEA), Henrik Enevoldsen (IOC-UNESCO), Esther Garrido Gamarro (FAO), Angelika Tritscher (WHO)

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New book

This volume on the Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (GEOHAB) is aimed at synthesizing the broad range of research and activities that took place during the nearly 2 decades of the international programme bearing this acronym. The central challenge for GEOHAB was to “understand the critical features and mechanisms underlying the population dynamics of HAB species in a variety of oceanographic regimes.” GEOHAB fostered research that was multi-faceted, multi-disciplinary, international and within an oceanographic context. With contributions from 69 authors from all over the world, this book reflects the global reach of the GEOHAB Programme.

There is no doubt that there are more harmful algal bloom (HAB) events, occurring more often, in more places and lasting longer than in decades past. It is now also well established that many of these events are the result of human activities, primarily through increased nutrient inputs – from land applications, direct sea applications (especially from aquaculture) and from atmospheric deposition, all of which have been increasing and have been altering the proportions and forms of nutrient loads. Species introductions are also occurring in ways and at rates not common in decades past, through ballast water and through transfer of materials in the aquaculture industry. As a result of these human activities, blooms are having more ecological, economic and human health impacts. As stated in the

GEOHAB Science Plan (2001), “these occurrences of toxic or harmful microalgae represent a significant and seemingly expanding threat to human health, fishery resources, and marine ecosystems throughout the world.”

This volume aims to capture the key focus areas of research under the GEOHAB umbrella. It introduces readers to the overarching framework of GEOHAB, factors contributing to the global expansion of HABs, the complexities of HABs in different habitats, and the forward-looking issues to be tackled by the next generation of GEOHAB, GlobalHAB.

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12th Advanced Phytoplankton Course - APC 12

Identification, Taxonomy, Systematics

Roscoff Biological Station (France) - 19th May to 8th June 2019

APC12 is organized by the Station Biologique de Roscoff together with the Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn and the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae.

APC 12 aims to provide participants with in-depth expert knowledge on the identification, classification and phylogeny of marine microalgae (diatoms, dinoflagellates, coccolithophores, other phytoflagellates) by integrating morphological observations with molecular data and new approaches.

The intensive 3-week course will consist of lectures, practical sessions and guest seminars. A diverse collection of preserved and live material will be offered for examination in light and (for selected taxa) electron microscopy. The course will cover: methods and criteria for species identification; up-to-date taxonomic frameworks; morphological and molecular phylogeny; toxic and harmful species; general and specific aspects of phytoplankton biodiversity and biogeography.

Faculty

- **Cedric Berney, Station Biologique de Roscoff, France - Eukaryotes**
- **Nicolas Chomerat, IFREMER, France - Dinoflagellates**
- **Mona Hoppenrath, Senckenberg Am Meer Wilhelmshaven, Germany - Dinoflagellates**
- **Raffaele Siano, IFREMER, France - Dinoflagellates**
- **Marina Montresor, Stazione Zoologica di Napoli, Italy - Dinoflagellates**
- **Jacob Larsen, University of Copenhagen, Denmark - Dinoflagellates**
- **Carina B. Lange, Universidad de Concepcion, Chile - Diatoms**
- **Nina Lundholm, Nat. History Museum, University of Copenhagen, Denmark - Diatoms**
- **Carmelo Tomas, University of South Carolina, Wilmington - Raphidophytes**
- **Diana Sarno, Stazione Zoologica di Napoli, Italy - Diatoms**
- **Kerstin Hoef-Emden, University of Köln, Germany - Cryptophytes**
- **Adriana Zingone, Stazione Zoologica di Napoli, Italy - Chlorophytes**
- **Øjvind Moestrup, University of Copenhagen, Denmark - Chlorophytes**
- **Daniel Vaultot, Station Biologique de Roscoff, France - Chlorophytes**
- **Masanobu Kawachi, NIES, Tsukuba, Japan - Heterokonts**
- **Ian Probert, Station Biologique de Roscoff, France - Haptophytes**
- **Bente Edvardsen, University of Oslo, Norway - Haptophytes**
- **Jeremy Young, University College London, UK - Haptophytes**
- **Christophe Six, Station Biologique de Roscoff, France - Cyanophytes**

Participation is limited to 20 participants with at least a M.Sc. degree (or equivalent), with documented experience and professional interest in phytoplankton identification. The course will be taught in English and a good knowledge of English is therefore required. There will be no registration fee, but participants will have to provide for their travel expenses.

More detailed information are available on the website: <https://sites.google.com/view/apc12/home>.

Please apply **before September 1, 2018** at <https://sites.google.com/view/apc12/applications>

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ISSHA will have a limited amount of travel awards for students and postdoctoral investigators to attend the conference, decisions will be announced early July.

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 61:

1 September 2018

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